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Internal Security Forces Hospital ETHICS COMMITTEE APPROVAL

Project title: Follow-up of patients after COVID 19 pneumonia : Incidence and predictive factors of hyperventilation syndrome in patients after COVID 19 pneumonia

Lead Principal Investigator: Dr Cherif Hela

Nature of Project: Prospective study

Local Chief Investigator: Dr Cherif Hela

Project Contact Point: *Pulmonology Departement*

Supervisor: PR CHARFI MOHAMED RIDHA

Hospital: FSI Hospital

Approval Number:

Members of Internal Security Forces Hospital Ethics Committee (ISFHEC).

Pr Ag Mohamed Taieb JOMNI (MD, Chairperson), Pr Ag Wassim HMAIED (MD), Pr Ag Mehdi CHARFI (MD), Pr Ag Syrine BELLAKHAL (MD), Dr Houneida BOUSSAFFA (MD), Dr Mehrez AJMI (MD), Mr Moez LABIDI (representative of the administration).

Date: 16/09/2020

Professor Ag Mohamed Taieb JOMNI
Chairperson

N° = 07 / 2020

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Study Protocol

Type, location and duration of the study

This prospective cohort study will follow –up a cohort of patients with laboratory-confirmed COVID-19 pneumonia. The follow up will begin September 2020 at the pulmonology outpatient clinic of the internal security forces hospital

Inclusion criteria

Patients aged 18 years and older with a SARS-COV-2 pneumonia will be included. The diagnosis was confirmed by the detection of the SARS-COV-2 viral genoma in the upper airways using RT-PCR on nasopharyngeal swabs with a chest CT scan indicating a COVID-19 infection at admission.

Non-Inclusion criteria

Patients who declined to take part in the study.
Files and scores with multiple missing data.
Patients without a confirmed SARS-COV-2 infection.
Patients with normal chest CT scan at admission.

Study design

- Inclusion at Hospital Discharge

Clinical characteristics (comorbidities and symptoms), presence and level of dyspnea assessed by the modified Medical Research Council (mMRC) dyspnea scale, presence of pulmonary embolism, admission to intensive care unit (ICU), high flow oxygen therapy, and anticoagulation treatments administered.

- The follow up will be scheduled at one month (M1)

- a. Post covid follow-up questionnaire

A list of symptoms that could be related to SARS-COV2 infection will be developed that allowed assessment of initial, persistent, or newly developed symptoms. These symptoms included fever, cough, fatigue, chest tightness, myalgia, dyspnea, diarrhea, nausea/vomiting, ageusia, anosmia, headache, arthralgia, and dizziness. Patients will be asked to report any persistent or newly occurring symptoms. The response options will be "yes or no".

- b. mMRC dyspnea scores

The modified Medical Research Council (mMRC) scale will be employed to evaluate the evolution of dyspnea

- c. Nijmegen Questionnaire

The Nijmegen score assesses the clinical probability of hyperventilation syndrome (HVS) according to 16 items and will be performed at the M1 follow-up. A score > 22/64 is suggestive of HVS (25).

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d. Arterial blood gas test (ABG)

Patients will undergo an arterial blood gas (ABG) test to measure the levels of various gasses, including oxygen and carbon dioxide, in the blood. This test was used to evaluate lung function and the body's ability to exchange gasses. The following measures to be taken: PaO₂: The partial pressure of oxygen in the arterial blood, PaCO₂: The partial pressure of carbon dioxide in the arterial blood, pH: The acidity or alkalinity of the blood, HCO₃⁻: The bicarbonate level in the blood.

e. PTSD Checklist for DSM-5 (PCL-5)

Screening for post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) was performed using the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorder Checklist 5 questionnaire validated in Arabic. A 20-item self-report measure that assesses the 20 DSM-5 symptoms of PTSD will be used for making the diagnosis when the score was > 32 (26–28).

f. The Post-COVID-19 Functional Status (PCFS) score

The alteration of the Functional Status was assessed by the post-COVID-19 Functional Status (PCFS) score (29,30). This is a validated questionnaire in Arabic containing 5 items. Each item represents a more profound alteration in the Functional Status. This PCFS score covers functional limitations, including changes in lifestyle and physical activities. Symptoms include but are not limited to dyspnea, pain, fatigue, muscle weakness, memory loss, anxiety, and depression. Patients will be categorized into 5 grades ranging from 0 (no functional limitations) to 4 (severe functional limitations).

Informed consent

Verbal informed consent from participants will be obtained subsequent to the comprehensive explanation of the study's procedures and objectives. Verbal consent was chosen to minimize physical contact and handling of documents to reduce the risk of transmission.

Funding:

No sources of funding or grants have been secured for this research

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